

INFLUENCE OF DISPERSION METHOD TO DISPERSIBILITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ULTRA-THIN CARBON FIBER TAPE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

UT-CTT (ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics) used in this study was developed as a lightweight material for the improvement of fuel efficiency of mass-production vehicles and this material showed as high mechanical properties as those of thermosetting CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) for airplane structures. Relatedly, researches on CTT have been actively performed recently. Especially, theoretical methodology to estimate the modulus and their variance was proposed [Zhang, 2015], but verification of this methodology in actual material has not been performed yet. So, the objective of this study is to experimentally verify the applicable range of the methodology, and to elucidate the cause of the difference between theory and experiment. If applicable range of the theory to predict mechanical properties is clearly verified from both experimental and theoretical viewpoints, it is a quite important finding in the practical application of CTT. Using statistical hypothesis test, the applicable limit of theoretical formula is shown, but this is shown only as a range because mechanical test was discretely performed. By C-scan, it is shown that there is no clear relationship between distribution of V_f within one specimen and variance of tensile modulus. On the other hand, average density seems to have relationship with variance of tensile modulus. In addition, from the results of optical microscopic observation, one of the reasons of the difference between theoretical assumption and actual material. That is to say, there are some gaps attributed to the edge of tapes. In the case of thick plate, the gap is smoothly filled with carbon fiber, but in the case of thin plate composed of small number of layers, the flowability is limited, so it can't be filled with carbon fiber smoothly.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

CTT (chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics) is one of the lightweight materials developed for the improvement of fuel efficiency of mass-production vehicles. And this material has as high mechanical properties as that of thermosetting CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) for airplane structure. So researches on not only fibers [1], but also on this type of intermediate material have been actively performed [2-7]. CTT can solve the problems of conventional materials such as low productivity and difficulty to adapt complex shapes, so it is expected as the material for primary structure of mass-production vehicle. However, the length of the chopped tapes in this material is usually several centimeters, so variance of mechanical properties in the evaluation by small specimens and that in small members have been an important problem. So, in recent years, prediction model of the mechanical properties has been constructed for the reduction of costs for material testing or the optimum design and so on [8, 9]. Among them, Zhang [10] proposed a simple and useful model based on a stochastic investigation. Zhang's theory can estimate not only tensile modulus itself, but also its variance. Indicated applicable range is valid under the assumption of model (homogeneity of material),

but it has not been verified for the actual material. Hence the objective of this paper is to experimentally verify the applicable range of the theory, and to elucidate the cause of the difference between theory and experiment. If applicable range of theory to predict mechanical properties of CTT especially for thin plate is clearly verified from both experiment and theory, it is a quite important finding in the practical application of CTT.

1.2 Prediction model for tensile modulus of CTT [10]

Prediction equation for the mean value and the variance of the tensile modulus of CTT has been proposed by Zhang [10]. There are three parameters, p , q , r , for how many tapes are in the measurement volume.

$$p = \frac{T}{t}, \quad q = \frac{W}{\sqrt{lw}}, \quad r = \frac{L}{\sqrt{lw}} \quad (1)$$

where T is thickness of specimen and t is that of chopped tape, W is width of specimen and w is that of chopped tape, L is gauge length in the specimen and l is length of chopped tape. Applicable range of this model is theoretically shown as $p > 10$. Then, the mean value, μ_{spec} , and the variance, σ_{spec}^2 , of the tensile modulus of CTT can be predicted by following formula.

$$\mu_{spec} = -\frac{A}{p} + B \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{spec}^2 = \left(-\frac{C}{p^2} + \frac{D}{p} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{q} - \frac{d_q - d_q^2}{q^2} \right\} \left\{ \frac{1}{r} - \frac{d_r - d_r^2}{r^2} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where A , B , C , D are constants determined by the kinds of tape. In order to lead the equations (2) and (3), Zhang used a simple model. First, tapes are converted to a square of equal area and the angle of each tape was given as a random number in 2-D plane. Next, necessary number of tapes were stacked in the thickness direction according to classical laminate theory. Furthermore, stacked tapes were summed according to superposition principle of equal strain condition about the width direction (the direction perpendicular to the direction of tensile load). Finally, they were summed according to superposition principle in the condition of equal stress about the longitudinal direction (the direction of tensile load) to obtain the elastic modulus of the whole specimen. A , B , C and D can be obtained by calculating tensile modulus using this model and determining the approximate curve by plotting various graphs. Four basic elastic constants shown in Table 1 are required to determine A , B , C and D . These values are dependent on the kinds of tape.

Table 1: Elastic properties of ultra-thin tape used in this study.

Young's modulus of 0° direction E_1 (GPa)	Young's modulus of 90° direction E_2 (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	In-plane shear modulus G_{12} (GPa)
120	6.8	0.3	1.2

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Material

The material used in this study was unidirectional CF/PA6 (Polyamide 6) prepreg sheet with the thickness of 44 μm , and the carbon fiber volume fraction (V_f) is about 55%. Carbon fiber was provided by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd, and PA6 was provided by Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc. This sheet was made by using tow spreading technology of Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. These kinds of technologies recently attract attention because of its improvement of some mechanical properties [11-14].

In order to cut the sheet to chopped tapes, an automated tape cutter and Tomson cutter were used. The length of the tapes is 18 mm and the width is 5 mm. The chopped tapes were dispersed by wet dispersion process (Figure 1) and the dispersed tapes are briefly heated and compressed to make fixed and portable sheet. This procedure can also prevent tapes from orientating out-of plane direction.

A steel mould with 125 x 250 mm² was used for compression moulding. The temporarily fixed sheets were laminated and placed into this mould. Thickness of specimens was varied by changing the number of temporarily fixed sheets. Number of the sheets was 2, 3, 4, 5, 7 and 13. The temperature of the mould was up to 255 °C. Moulding pressure was first 1 MPa and maintained 10 minutes and the pressure was increased up to 5 MPa and maintained 15 minutes. It was cooled down to below around 60 °C and CTT plate was removed from the mould. The plates prepared by the procedure are dried in the vacuum dryer at 90 °C.

All CTT used in this study was made from thin prepreg sheet by tow spreading technology, so it is called UT-CTT (ultra-thin carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics) (Figure 2) in the following.

Figure 1: Dispersion equipment of wet process.

Figure 2: Appearance of UT-CTT.

2.2 Mechanical testing procedure

Six specimens for tensile test were cut from one plate with each thickness. The width of specimen is 35 mm and the length is 120 mm. Thickness of specimens is shown in Table 2. Average V_f and its coefficient of variation was calculated from the measurement results of specific gravity and dimensions of each specimen. The results are shown in Table 3.

Non-destructive tensile test was performed with stroke speed of 1.0 mm/min. Tensile modulus was calculated from stress-strain curve. Basically, strain range used for the calculation of tensile modulus was 0.2% with a start point of 0.05% and an end point of 0.25%. If the curve warps so much, we use the other part of the curve which is straight enough. The number of tests was six for each thickness.

Table 2: Thickness of specimens.

ply	2	3*	3	3*	4	5	7	13
Thickness [mm]	0.33	0.48	0.50	0.50	0.65	0.78	1.09	2.03

Table 3: Average V_f and coefficient of variation.

ply	2	3*	3	3*	4	5	7	13
Average V_f [%]	50.3	55.8	54.8	54.6	55.3	55.8	54.5	56.1
CV [%]	5.2	2.6	3.2	1.8	0.3	0.8	0.7	0.9

*tape width = 10 mm

**tape length = 12 mm

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Comparison between experimental and prediction results

Figures 3-5 show a comparison of each test results and the theoretical value calculated by Zhang's theory. Gauge length for each results is 20, 40 and 60 mm, respectively. E_{calc} is the mean value and CV_{calc} is the coefficient of variation of the tensile modulus, which are calculated from the theory. E_{exp} and CV_{exp} are experimental value. 1σ interval from E_{calc} is shown as error bars. From these figures, although the tensile modulus tends to exhibit a somewhat lower average, it is included in the 1σ interval. It was found that theoretical formula is applicable in $p > 10$ as introduced in section 1.2.

For the coefficient of variation, these figures show that experimental value tend to be larger than theoretical value when specimen is thinner than about 0.5 mm to 0.65 mm. Tape thickness is 0.044 mm, so it means that there is a limit from $p = 11$ to $p = 15$. " q " is fixed in this paper, so further study is necessary. Effect of r is referred to as small, but it seems that the variation of the CV of 60 mm is smaller than that of 20 mm and 40 mm, so especially in the case of thin material, r is presumed to be an important factor.

The application limit of the assumption for fixing the position of tapes in the model is thought to be one of the reason that variation increased when p becomes smaller. That is, in Zhang's model, only the angle of tape is random and location of tapes is fixed, but the location has certain degree of bias in practice. As number of tapes in the thickness direction increases when the plate thickness is thick, the bias is negligible. On the other hand, when the plate is thin, unevenness in the number of tape overlapping are not negligible, then the assumption of the uniform dispersion is considered to be no longer hold.

In the case of plate thinner than 1 mm, there is a limit of applicable range of theory. However, not only this, but also q and r affect whether molding of plate goes well or not, and affect scatter of tensile modulus. For example, in this paper, the effect of q and r was investigated by changing the width of tapes. As a result, if the width of tapes became wider, such as 10 mm, some tapes were folded along the fiber direction like Figure 6. Therefore, it was found that the size of tapes affects dispersion of tapes and this is one of the reason of difference between theory and actual phenomena. So the size of

tapes has to be taken into account to disperse tapes well. Further study about relationship between the value of q , r and the condition of dispersion or molding is a future task.

Figure 3: Comparison of E and CV of theoretical and experimental value (gauge length: 20 mm).

Figure 4: Comparison of E and CV of theoretical and experimental value (gauge length: 40 mm).

Figure 5: Comparison of E and CV of theoretical and experimental value (gauge length: 60 mm).

Figure 6: Chopped tapes folded along fiber direction (width of tape: 10 mm).

3.2 Evaluation of difference between experimental and prediction results

First, we verified whether the difference between the experimental results and the theoretical value is within an error or reckoned as different value using a statistical hypothesis test.

Concerning tensile modulus, the experimental results and theoretical values show good agreement as shown in Figures 7 and 8. Figures 9 and 10 show CV of density and CV_{exp} / CV_{calc} , and these horizontal axis is p and pqr , respectively. In these figures, if the experimental value is rejected by statistical hypothesis testing, x is written on its marker. It was found that the experimental results tend to be out of the error range of the theory in the case of thin specimen. That is, it can be said that the result did not show good agreement with the theoretical value in thin specimen. In addition, from Figure 9, variance of density may have relationship with limit of applicable range of theory. From Figures 9 and 10, it was found that the limit is in the range of p from 11 to 15, and that of pqr is in the range from 250 to 300.

Then, the distribution of V_f was observed by a double transmission method using ultrasonic flaw detector, C-scan. Intensity of ultrasonic incident waves was set to a constant value and intensity of reflected waves was measured. Then, the distribution of relatively high and low V_f in the specimen can be observed. As a result of the observation, relationship between the variation of V_f in the C-Scan image and the value of elastic modulus cannot be found. This is similarly found in the study by Feraboli et al. [7], that is, there is no clear relationship between the failure part and C-Scan image.

Moreover, cross section of specimen was observed by using an optical microscope. It was found that there were gaps at the ends of the tapes by lamination. Also, there was a tendency that these gaps easily exist in a thin plate such as the left picture of Figure 11, but the other tape filled the gaps in a thicker plate such as the right picture of Figure 11.

Figure 7: Relationship between p and E_{exp} / E_{calc} .

Figure 8: Relationship between pqr and E_{exp} / E_{calc} .

Figure 9: CV of density and relationship between p and CV_{exp} / CV_{calc} .

Figure 10: Relationship between pqr and CV_{exp} / CV_{calc} .

Figure 11; Cross section image of thin and thick plate (left: $p = 5$, right: $p = 13$).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated about the applicable range of Zhang's theory [10] to predict tensile modulus and its variance. The following conclusions were obtained.

- Concerning the variance of tensile modulus of UT-CTT, it is shown that there is an applicable limit of theoretical formula. Zhang's theory indicate good coincidence with experiment in $p > 15$ and $pqr > 250$. This limit is attributed to the difference in the actual state of the material and assumption of theoretical formula. $p > 15$ is equivalent to thickness > 0.66 mm. In the case of tape of $5 \text{ mm} \times 18 \text{ mm}$, $pqr > 250$ is equivalent to the length > 33 mm in a plate having thickness of 2 mm and width of 15 mm. Therefore, it is concluded that Zhang's theory is practical since it can be applicable to evaluate mechanical properties using small specimens and evaluate performance of structural member even if the size is small.
- The possible reason why the theory cannot be applied in specific range is the gaps at the edge of chopped tapes. In the case of thick plate, the gap is smoothly filled with carbon fiber in another tapes. On the other hand, in the case of thin plate composed of small number of layers, the flowability of the tapes is limited, so the gaps cannot be smoothly filled with carbon fiber.

Based on the results of this study, if the applicable range of Zhang's theory is investigated under dynamic load, in high humidity condition and so on, it would be useful to the practical application of UT-CTT in automotive structures.

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